

GLASS MATRIX COMPOSITES - I - GRAPHITE FIBER REINFORCED GLASS

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The mechanical properties of graphite fiber reinforced glass are described and it is demonstrated that this system offers unique possibilities as a high performance structural material. Graphite fibers of Hercules HMS and HTS, Thornel 300 and Celanese DG-102 were used to reinforce, both uniaxially and biaxially, a borosilicate pyrex glass. Composite flexural strength distribution, strength as a function of test temperature, fracture toughness and oxidative stability were determined and shown to be primarily a function of fiber type and the quality of fiber-matrix bond formed during composite fabrication.

Introduction

Although a wide variety of resin and metal matrix composites have been developed using high specific property fibers, very few of these systems permit use at temperatures above 400°C. The problem of fiber-matrix compatibility has made the extension into this temperature range difficult. Those metal matrix composites which have succeeded in projecting into this higher temperature regime have also presented the engineer with a significant increase in density above resin matrix composites. The systems listed in Table I are those currently available, with the most attractive specific properties up to 700°C. Also included in the table are two glass matrix composites which offer the potential for providing both high specific properties and low density. Glass matrix composite systems are unique in this capability and it will be shown in this and a companion paper (1) that they can combine the virtues of excellent structural performance, low density, environmental stability and low cost (both material and fabrication).

Of the two glass matrix composite systems listed in Table I, it is the graphite reinforced system which provides the highest levels of structural performance. Graphite reinforced glass will be discussed in this paper and the alumina reinforced glass system will be presented in another paper in this conference (1).

Previous research on graphite reinforced glass demonstrated the potential for this composite system (2-5). Successful fabrication procedures were developed based on the use of glass powder slurries, which infiltrated graphite fiber bundles, and the subsequent hot pressing of composites. Mechanical test data obtained at that time confirmed the possibility of achieving reinforcement of the brittle glass matrix.

The herein described program has extended these previous findings and is part of a larger effort to achieve the application of graphite reinforced glass composites in aerospace structures (6).

Table I. Comparison of Composite Systems

Composite System	Density (gm/cc)	Maximum Use Temperature (°C)
Graphite-Epoxy	1.6	200
Graphite-Polyimide	1.6	300
Graphite-Glass	2.0	650
Graphite-Aluminum	2.3	325
Boron-Aluminum	2.7	325
FP Alumina-Glass	3.1	>650
Boron-Titanium	3.7	650

Experimental

The overall program (6) has dealt with a wide range of graphite fibers and glass matrices, however, the composites described in this paper were fabricated using three graphite fibers and one glass matrix, Table II. The 7740 glass matrix is a Corning Glass borosilicate, better known as Pyrex, composition which is widely used in common glassware because of its high thermal shock resistance, chemical inertness, and reasonably high thermal stability. All composites were fabricated in a two step process. First, precursor tapes were made, consisting of graphite fibers infiltrated with finely divided glass powder. These tapes were then cut and stacked in graphite dies for hot pressing in an inert atmosphere. Further details of the tape fabrication and hot pressing procedures can be found in reference (6).

The mechanical test procedures used included three point bend, four point bend with strain gauging, and fracture toughness testing. This last test was performed on notched, rectangular cross sectioned three point bend bars with values of fracture toughness calculated using the maximum loads achieved prior to failure. The toughness tests were performed at loading rates of 0.127 cm per minute (hydraulic test machine) and 20,000 cm per minute (pendulum impact machine with strain gauged tup for load vs time read out).

Table II. Materials Used

Materials	Density (gm/cm ³)	Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
Hercules HTS Fiber	1.66	257	2830
Hercules HMS Fiber	1.80	350	2700
Thornel 300s Fiber	1.75	228	2650
Celanese DG-102 Fiber	1.95	530	1725
7740 Pyrex Glass Matrix	2.23	63	--

Prior to test all specimens were uniformly surface ground with a diamond grinding wheel. This resulted in the exposure of graphite fibers on the surfaces of all composites.

Results

Microstructure

The fabrication procedures used were capable of providing fully dense composites containing 50 to 60% by volume of well dispersed fibers. The polished microstructures, and overall composite appearance, were found to be very similar to those of resin matrix composites. The microstructure of a unidirectionally reinforced composite of HMS fiber in 7740 pyrex glass is shown in Figure 1a.

Figure 1. Microstructures of HMS fiber reinforced 7740 glass composites (a) unidirectionally reinforced, (b) 0/90 cross ply reinforced.

Due to the use of a 1200°C pressing temperature, and 13.8 MPa pressure, the glass matrix has completely filled the areas surrounding the individual graphite fibers. A 0/90 cross ply composite structure, Figure 1b, illustrates this same point, as well as the ability to make a uniformly structured multi-axially reinforced material. It was noted that some matrix cracking occurs parallel to the fibers in the cross ply specimen due to the anisotropy of thermal expansion. The thermal expansion of a unidirectional composite ply is approximately -0.5×10^{-6} per °C in the axial direction and $+4 \times 10^{-6}$ per °C in the transverse direction (6). Thus, on cooling from the hot pressing temperature, an internal stress state is generated which causes cracking in a direction parallel to the fibers.

Axial Strength

The 0° strength of unidirectionally reinforced composites was found to be strongly dependent on fiber type. The three point bend data presented in Figure 2 are typical of the flexural strengths obtained at 22°C. In each fiber case nine bend specimens were tested and the individual data points are plotted on a cumulative probability for failure basis. The average values of strength are 689 MPa for the HMS fiber reinforced 7740, 498 MPa for Thornel 300s in 7740, 370 MPa for HTS reinforced 7740, and 342 MPa for DG-102 reinforced 7740. These values of flexural strength are all less than those obtainable from resin matrix composites containing the same fibers and also tested at 22°C. The values are, however, quite high and, also, in each fiber case, distributed over a relatively narrow range of values when compared to data typical of unreinforced ceramics and glasses.

Figure 2. Composite flexural strength, determined by three point bend, for 7740 Pyrex glass matrix composites unidirectionally reinforced with the indicated fibers. Each indicated data point represents a specimen test.

Typical stress strain curves, obtained from strain gauged four point bend specimens, are presented in Figure 3. These data, for HMS fiber reinforced 7740 glass have been used to obtain values of axial elastic moduli and failure strain. The measured primary elastic modulus values (E_1) are in reasonably close agreement with those calculated for a composite containing 50% by volume of fiber and in the case of specimen number one, the observation of a secondary modulus (E_2) suggests a transition from a region in which purely elastic deformation is taking place, to a region where the matrix is undergoing local tensile failure and the fibers are still deforming elastically. This is representative of a brittle fiber plus brittle matrix system at 22°C where the failure strain of the fibers exceeds that of the glass matrix.

Figure 3. Stress vs strain curves for 0° HMS fiber reinforced 7740 glass at 22°C. For specimen (1) $E_1 = 200$ GPa, $E_2 = 180$ GPa, UTS = 597 MPa, $\epsilon_f = 0.29\%$. For specimen (2) $E_1 = 185$ GPa, UTS = 472 MPa, $\epsilon_f = 0.26\%$. Curves obtained using strain gauges on the tension side of a 4 point bend test.

This behavior is altered significantly, however, if mechanical tests are run at elevated temperatures where the failure strain of the matrix is increased significantly. The three point bend test data in Figure 4 demonstrate this. The curves shown represent the applied load vs resultant deflection for 0° HMS reinforced 7740 specimens tested at various indicated temperatures.

in an argon atmosphere. The appearance of the 22°C curve is different from those in Figure 3 because it illustrates the progressive failure of the entire three point bend specimen. Thus, as shown by the step wise decrease in load, crack propagation is difficult in this material and additional deflection (or load) must be applied to carry through to fracture of the entire specimen. In the case of Figure 3, the strain gauge only recorded failure of the material right at the tensile surface of the flexural beam.

All of the specimens tested to obtain the curves in Figure 4 were of approximately the same size. Thus, it can also be seen that the strength of this composite type increases significantly with increasing temperature up to approximately 600-650°C. This strength increase is shown more clearly in Figure 5 where the actual values of flexural strength are presented along with those for other composites. The indicated increase in strength is due to the increase in failure strain of the matrix with increasing test temperature. Thus, with a maximum strength of approximately 1200 MPa at 600°C for HMS reinforced 7740, the level of performance of resin matrix composites tested at 22°C has been achieved. This was demonstrated with specimens of HMS fiber reinforced polysulfone and polyethersulfone which were also tested in three point bend. These data are presented in Figure 5 as resin matrix composite strength measurements made over the temperature range of 22°C to 200°C.

Figure 4. Applied load vs measured mid span deflection curves for the three point bend testing of 0° HMS fiber reinforced 7740 glass. The elevated temperature tests were all run in an inert atmosphere.

Several temperatures of importance have been indicated in Figure 5. Temperatures T_1 and T_2 refer to the strain and annealing points respectively of 7740 pyrex glass. Both of these values correspond to temperatures at which particular values of glass viscosity are achieved and are representative of the decrease in glass viscosity with increasing temperature. Temperatures T_3 and T_4 refer to the glass transition temperatures of the polysulfone and polyethersulfone respectively and also correspond to regions of major decrease in matrix viscosity. For the resin matrix composites, it was not possible to fracture three point bend specimens at test temperatures near T_3 or T_4 . Instead, the

specimens simply bent without fiber fracture due to the low matrix shear strength. Similarly, it was not possible to fracture glass matrix composite specimens above 650°C. Instead, they deformed extensively with rounded load deflection traces such as the one shown in Figure 4 for the 700°C test of HMS fiber reinforced 7740 glass.

Figure 5. Composite flexural strength as a function of test temperature for glass matrix and resin matrix composites.

- 0° HMS reinforced 7740 glass
 - ◆ 0° DG-102 reinforced 7740 glass
 - 0° HMS reinforced polyethersulfone resin
 - ▲ 0° HMS reinforced polysulfone resin
- The indicated temperatures are T_1 = strain point of 7740 glass, T_2 = annealing point of 7740 glass, T_3 = glass transition temperature of polysulfone, T_4 = glass transition temperature of polyethersulfone.

The flexural strength of Celanese DG-102 fiber reinforced 7740 glass is also presented in Figure 5 as a function of test temperature. Although the values of strength are lower than those for HMS 7740, they present a similar trend of behavior.

Fracture Toughness

The data obtained from the three point bend fracture toughness testing of prenotched specimens are presented in Table III. Both the fracture toughness values, K_{Ic} and energy dissipated to total fracture per unit area of specimen cross section are given for 22°C, 600°C and 650°C. The value of fracture toughness was not found to be sensitive to test speed at 22°C, however, there is a variation with test temperature with a significantly lower value measured at approximately 600°C. This is also the temperature at which the maximum value of flexural strength was measured, Figure 5.

Table III. Fracture Toughness Data for 0° HMS Fiber Reinforced 7740

Test Speed (cm/min)	Test Temp. °C	K _c MN/m ^{3/2}	Energy Per Unit Area Joules/m ²
20,000	22	21.4	23,500
0.127	22	22.1	--
20,000	600	15.8	10,600
20,000	650	19.0	11,800

Transverse Strength

The transverse strength of HMS and HTS fiber reinforced composites was measured by three point bend and found to be quite low. The 22°C flexural strength of 90° HMS reinforced 7740 glass ranged from 6.8 MPa to 22.2 MPa with an average value of 12.5 MPa while the average for HTS reinforced 7740 specimens was 10.8 MPa with a range of 4.7 to 18.0 MPa. Both of these data sets reflect the low fiber-matrix bond strength which, as will be discussed, is of major importance in controlling both axial and transverse composite behavior.

Biaxial Reinforcement

Because of the very low levels of transverse strength, it is important to consider the fabrication and properties of multiaxially reinforced specimens. This has been done for cross plied HMS fiber reinforced 7740 using two different ply stack up sequences, Table IV. In almost every case the specimens failed in an interlaminar mode rather than tensile mode so that the indicated values are probably less than the true composite flexural strength.

Table IV. Flexural Strength of HMS Fiber Reinforced 7740 Glass

Ply Lay Up Sequence	Flexural Strength (MPa)*	
	Range	Avg.
[(0 ₂ 90 ₂) ₂] _s	198 - 228	217
[(0/90) ₄] _s	172 - 284	225

* Calculated although all but one specimen failed in an interlaminar mode rather than tensile mode.

Oxidative Stability

Because of the anticipated use of these composites at elevated temperatures, several specimens from each type have been exposed to air and argon environments for a period of 4 hours at 560°C. The average values of strength

measured before and after exposure are given in Table V. The two highest strength composite types containing HMS and Thornel 300 fiber exhibited considerable degradation due to exposure to air while the lower strength HTS and DG-102 reinforced systems did not.

Table V. Four Hour Thermal Exposure of 7740 Glass Matrix Composites at 560°C

Fiber Type	Average Composite Three Point Bend Strength Values (MPa)		
	As Fabricated	After Argon Exposure	After Air Exposure
HMS	635	660	470
Thornel 300s	490	250	122
HTS	350	390	335
DG-102	235	263	226

Discussion

The preceding data have demonstrated that graphite fiber reinforced glass matrix composites can be considered as an extension of current resin matrix technology. Similarities between composite properties can clearly be seen if it is recognized that the glass matrix systems must be tested at much higher temperatures than their resin matrix counterparts.

It has also been shown that, although both fiber and matrix can be considered classically brittle materials, the resultant composite is not. This is most clearly demonstrated by the high level of fracture toughness measured and is due to the debonding between fiber and matrix, which takes place as a crack front attempts to propagate through the composite. Phillips (5) has demonstrated the importance of this fiber-matrix interfacial strength in controlling crack growth resistance, and the herein reported values of K_c agree well with those measured by Phillips for a high modulus graphite fiber reinforced Pyrex composite.

The importance of interfacial strength, however, goes beyond its influence on fracture toughness. As was shown in Figure 2, the measured strength of composites could not be simply related to the strength of the reinforcing fibers. Had this been the case the HTS reinforced system would have been as strong, or even stronger than, the HMS and T-300 reinforced composites. This, however, was not the case. Instead, it behaved much more like the DG-102 reinforced glass and this similarity appears to be due to the fact that both of these composites exhibited similar failure modes. In the case of HTS and DG-102 reinforced glass there was very little fiber-matrix debonding during fracture. This higher bond strength is also the probable cause for the superior oxidation resistance of these composites when compared with HMS and T-300 specimens which exhibited extensive fiber-matrix debonding during fracture.

To help the reader understand better the structural performance benefits of graphite fiber reinforced glass, comparison will be made with already well

known composite systems. The data in Figure 6 present the flexural strength divided by density of two metal matrix composite systems, and HMS reinforced 7740 glass, as a function of test temperature. The flexural strength of composites was used, rather than tensile strength, because it includes a larger contribution of matrix performance. Thus, in the case of the Th-50 graphite reinforced aluminum, the melting of the aluminum alloy at approximately 580°C causes a drastic drop in composite strength above 350°C. This is why all aluminum matrix composites are limited in their application temperature due to excessive matrix creep and strength decrease. In contrast, the Borsic reinforced titanium performance is hampered not by the thermal stability of the matrix, but by the higher density of the system. It must be noted, however, that the HMS reinforced glass system was tested in an inert atmosphere to prevent degradation. Without this precaution the composite strength would be considerably lower. Nevertheless, the comparison is important and clearly demonstrates the structural potential for this system at lower temperatures, and if protected, at high temperatures.

A comparison with other materials based on composite fracture toughness is also possible, Table VI. These data point out that at 22°C the fracture toughness of 0° HMS reinforced 7740 is in the range of two high strength aluminum alloys and also conventional graphite reinforced epoxy.

Figure 6. Flexural strength divided by density for unidirectionally reinforced composites as a function of test temperature. The HMS graphite reinforced glass was tested in inert atmosphere while the other systems were tested in air. The data for the Th50 graphite reinforced aluminum were taken from reference (7).

Table VI. Fracture Toughness Comparison at 22°C

Materials	K_{IC} MN/m ^{3/2}
0° HMS 7740	21.7
Morganite II Epoxy (8)	
0°	35.0
90°	1.8
45°	2.5
±45°	19.7
0/±45°/90	24.0
2014-T6 Aluminum Alloy (9)	22.0
6061-T651 Aluminum Alloy (9)	30.0

From all of the above it can be concluded that graphite reinforced glass matrix composites can offer a unique combination of properties that, as yet, have not been matched with an application. Exceptional thermal stability, high specific strength and elastic modulus, excellent fracture toughness and high levels of chemical inertness should all combine to make this material and excellent choice for a wide variety of uses. It can also be projected that material cost will be quite low. The raw materials are inexpensive and because the hot pressing operation involves the deformation of a thermoplastic, the hot pressing time should be quite short. In addition, because of the thermoplastic nature of the matrix, secondary forming operations should also be readily possible.

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